

Us and Our Heroes

by Ramin Saadat

When I was a child, books were the most abundant thing in our home. You could always find someone tucked away in a corner, reading. Even when we gathered around the table for meals, we didn't talk about work or politics, we talked about what we'd been reading. For that, I consider myself very lucky.

But this upbringing had another side to it. I spent my childhood drifting through the worlds of stories and imaginary adventures, and those tales left a deep mark on me.

I was always imagining myself as the hero. In my childish daydreams, I'd charge at enemies on horseback, sword raised, while crowds cheered me on. In helmet and armour, I'd hunt demons and evil spirits through mountain passes. Or, after defeating the enemy, I'd stand at the bow of a great warship, flag in hand, sailing home in triumph.

It was during those years that I decided to compile a list of the world's great heroes from books and stories. Perhaps I thought to myself: if you can't actually be a hero, at least you can keep a record of their names.

And so I began, listing the names of the world's heroes, with a short note about each: which country they came from, when they lived, and what they did.

Bear in mind, this was before computers and the internet. I had to spend hours in our small town's public library, flipping through books, or asking anyone I knew with a bookish disposition about heroes from distant lands.

You can imagine what a challenge this was. For instance:

Every country and culture has its own mythological, historical, religious, and national heroes. Even small communities, towns, villages, even clans, have figures lodged in their collective memory, real or imagined, who were once honoured and admired. And then there were the complications: some heroes are remembered for their good deeds, others for betrayal, and some whose reputations were later destroyed because they had, as the stories go, sold their souls to the devil...

Because of all this, I decided to narrow my scope. I would only include someone if they met these criteria:

- They are mentioned warmly in everyday speech and popular culture, the kind of name ordinary people drop in conversation.
- Their name appears in school textbooks, so that children learn it when studying their national culture.
- Politicians invoke them when trying to stir the crowd, inspire pride, or boast to foreign leaders.
- Religious preachers mention them, or the villains who oppose them, when urging people toward virtue or warning them away from sin.
- Their name has become an adjective, when we want to describe someone, we reach for their name. We say: strong as Rostam, a betrayal like Judas, as mad as Don Quixote...

To cut a long story short: with these criteria, I finally assembled my golden list. Exactly 273 names.

I remember the number well, because for years afterwards I'd bring it up at every opportunity. I'd steer the conversation until I could ask:

Do you have any idea how many heroes have existed throughout the whole of human history?

Someone would venture a guess. And then I'd announce, as loudly as I could: No, exactly 273!

And I'd wait, hoping they'd ask: Where on earth did you get that number? so I could proudly tell them about my great heroic quest to find these names...

But they never asked. At most, they'd raise an eyebrow and say: How interesting.

No one ever asked what the names were, or where in the world they came from, which would have let me walk them (heroically, of course) through East Asia: China, Japan, India; then Iran, Greece, and Rome; across to Europe, Africa, and the Americas. I should mention that at the time, the United States hadn't yet produced a great historical hero, though more recently, we've seen someone by the name of Donald Trump step forward, dressed as Superman.

Years passed. Those notes and my golden list were lost to time. But that golden number stayed with me, until just a few days ago.

All of this is to say: I was recently re-reading the Epic of Gilgamesh (surely one of the oldest myths in the world) when the memory of that childhood number surfaced again, and a question formed in my mind. A question that sent me searching once more (this time with the help of the internet), and one I'd like to share with you.

Have you ever stopped to ask yourself: why do we venerate our historical, mythological, national, or religious heroes? What is the real reason behind this universal, timeless act of remembrance and praise, found in every culture, every nation, every faith?

I searched. I found answers. And I hope, if you'll bear with me, you might hear them out. Though I'll ask this of you: please, when I'm done, don't just raise an eyebrow and say: How interesting!

When I looked back at those 273 names, the first thing that struck me was this: most of them had been killed.

Not from old age or illness, but at the height of their strength and youth, in the service of a cause or a people. For example:

Among mythological and epic heroes from East and West: Yue Fei and Jing Ke (China), Okita Soji (Japan), Siyavash and Esfandiar (Iran), Baldr (Norse mythology), Siegfried (the Nibelungenlied, Germany), Achilles (Greece)... all met this same fate.

Among religious and spiritual figures: Jesus Christ, Imam Husayn, John the Baptist, Saint Stephen, Prahlada (Hindu mythology), Joan of Arc... martyred.

Among political and national fighters: Emiliano Zapata (Mexico), Sophie Scholl (Germany), Bobby Sands (Ireland), Omar Mukhtar (Libya), Che Guevara (Latin America)... all died fighting.

Among thinkers and reformers: Socrates (Greece), Hypatia (Alexandria), Giordano Bruno (Italy)... met a grim end.

It was as though an early death were the entry requirement for my golden list.

And so I asked myself: is this a coincidence, or a recurring pattern in history? Does the hero who survives get forgotten?

Consider Odysseus. He survived. He came home. He lived to old age. Yet Achilles -who died young- has lodged himself far more deeply in the memory of history. Why?

Could it be that we ordinary people, the custodians of civilisation, culture, and history, do not honour our heroes and our fallen out of love and affection? That what we actually need is not the hero, but the hero's death?

Perhaps the daily remembrance of a hero's glorious end serves a very particular purpose for those of us who have never been heroes ourselves. It creates a template, a deeply useful one, for us ordinary

people. A template that tells the next generation: sacrifice for your nation has value. Giving your life for others is an honour. Look how we revere our dead, strive to be like them, and you too shall be immortalised.

Which raises a rather uncomfortable question. Who, exactly, builds this template? Who decides which death is glorious and which is not?

Who is it that always lays flowers on the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier?

Politicians!

Who is it that weeps at the pulpit when speaking of martyrs, urging the faithful toward sacrifice?

Religious preachers!

Two groups who, more often than not, have never fought themselves, and whose greatest acts of heroism consist of giving speeches.

Does that not give you pause?

Perhaps this veneration is less a feeling and more a transaction. A deal in which ordinary people profit, and the hero pays. Put more plainly: perhaps we ordinary people are extracting a kind of forced labour from our bravest and most capable, at the price of our own inability to act.

And you can extend this logic even to sport. One person devotes their entire youth and life to a stadium and a training ground, exhausting themselves, so that we can cheer and hang a medal around their neck.

It is a strange human phenomenon. One that, with some caution, resembles the parasitic relationships we observe in the natural world.

Among chimpanzees, for instance, we see something similar: the older, wiler males encourage the young, energetic ones to fight at the borders, while they themselves wait safely at the centre of the group.

Or consider the Adélie penguins on the icy cliffs of Antarctica. When the flock wants to enter the water, there is always the threat of a leopard seal lurking below. The older penguins hang back, and with nudges and shoves, push one of the younger or weaker birds into the water. If it is taken by the seal, the water is dangerous and they retreat. If it survives and begins to swim, the rest (including the experienced elders) plunge in with confidence. They spend one life to purchase information and safety for the rest. From a biological standpoint, this may be justifiable, one life for many. From a human standpoint, it looks a great deal like exploitation.

In the world of ants (particularly the so-called legionary or army ants) we find something similar again. At the heart of the colony, the queen (the continuity of the species) is kept safe. When danger arrives (an enemy attack or a flood) a chemical signal (a pheromone) is released by the worker ants, sending the young soldiers into a kind of battle-frenzy. Without hesitation, they throw themselves toward death, building walls of their own bodies to protect the inner colony.

In a kind of metaphor, one might say: the scent of the pheromone plays the same role as the rousing speech, switching off the instinct for self-preservation, and activating the instinct to sacrifice oneself for the group.

All of this suggests that in our veneration of heroes, we are doing precisely what nature does to preserve a species: turning the individual into an instrument for the survival of the group. Whether that group is a colony of ants, a nation, or a motherland.

We will always -perhaps forever- lay flowers on the Tomb of the Unknown Soldier. Because that flower is a small price to pay to

ensure that in the next war, there will still be people willing to pay the heavy cost of dying in our place. It is a bitter thought. But it seems that our civilisation is nothing more than a more sophisticated version of the ant colony.

We praise our heroes. We give them medals. We weep for them. We name streets after them. Perhaps to quieten our conscience about this historical injustice. All the while unaware that those flowers are a down payment on the next sacrifice.

In a world that is still searching for heroes, perhaps what we are really searching for is someone to pay (with their life) for our own inaction and the failures of our systems.

Today, when I think back to that golden number - 273 - I no longer see it as a great discovery. I see it as a long invoice that humanity has been paying for its own survival.

Perhaps, in that little library in our small town, if someone had finally asked me: who are these people?

I should have said:

These are the people we convinced to die in our place. So that we could sit safely in a corner, read books, and romanticise the glory of their deaths. Perhaps our loudest cheers in praise of a hero are nothing more than a way to drown out the sound of our own knees trembling.

Now I understand why my listeners would only raise an eyebrow. Perhaps the most sensible response to this ancient and unjust transaction was always silence, and a quiet:
How interesting!
